

Coon and Tucker *“Measuring motivation for alfalfa hay in feedlot cattle using an aversive stimulus as a tradeoff”*

Description of the electrified barrier

The apparatus consisted of 3 parts: 1) the electrified barrier (Figure 1), 2) the pulley system that affixed the barrier to the feed bin (Figure 2), and 3) the animal shocker that electrified the barrier (Figure 3).

Each steer was trained to use the electrified barrier to access supplementary food in the automated feed bin. All animals also had access to a finishing ration fed ad-libitum in an adjacent automated feed bin that did not have an electrified barrier. In order to access the treatment diets, animals had to push against the electrified barrier with their muzzles.

Please see the supplementary videos “Confident visit.mp4” and “Unsuccessful attempt.mp4” for examples of animals using the electrified barrier.

Figure 1. Barrier design electrified using alligator clips (1) attached to an animal shocker (Precision Animal Shocker, model no. H13-17A, Coulburn Instruments, Holliston, MA, USA); description includes construction materials and measurements. A plywood board acted as the base for the barrier on which, 2 strips of plywood were nailed vertically along the right and left edge of the base (2). Inward from either strip of wood, 7 strips of plywood were nailed vertically (2). The strips of wood elevated the electrified metal to reduce resistance by eliminating points of contact between the metal and the plywood base. On top of these strips of wood, strips of rubber (4) (Silicone 1/16 in Commercial Grade 60A Rubber Sheet, Rubber-Cal, Fountain Valley, CA, USA) were laid to act as a barrier between the wood and the electrified metal. Without these rubber strips, atmospheric moisture might seep into the wood and reduce the conductivity of the metal. Metal fence wire (1/2 in 19-Gauge Galvanized Steel Hardware Cloth, Everbilt, Home Depot, Atlanta, GA, USA) was cut into two interlocking pieces (5). Then the two pieces were affixed to the barrier by stapling the metal to the elevated strips using wood staples (10mm Steel Staples, Arrow, Saddle Brook, NJ, USA). It was important that the two pieces of metal never touched or overlapped one another as this would cause the electric shock applied to the metal to short, meaning no shocking sensation was perceived. Along the bottom of the barrier another strip of plywood was nailed horizontally, on which 4 magnets were attached. These magnets (6) (2.99 mm Neodymium Super Disc Magnets, Master Magnetics, Castle Rock, CO, USA) were each encased in a duct tape pocket that was then folded into a square of vinyl (5.08 x 2.54 cm,

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Grip Prints White Shelf/Drawer Liner, Kittrich, Ponoma, CA, USA). The magnets were secured to the plywood strip by stapling the vinyl envelope to the wood. Four complimentary magnets are enclosed in their own duct-tape/vinyl envelopes and stapled to the RIC trough to secure the barrier when the trough is closed by connecting to the 4 magnets on the barrier. Finally, two holes were drilled into the plywood base for hanging (7); the holes sat 2.54 cm below the top edge of the base.

Figure 2. A) Electrified barrier (1) when in the elevated position using a pulley system (2) that secured the contraction to the automated feed bin (3). B) Electrified barrier in the lowered position. Electrified surface of barrier faced into the pen. A custom frame was built to attach a pulley system that raised and lowered the barrier when an animal accessed the feed bin. The metal frame for the pulley system was attached to the top of the feed bin using 2 screws. Two S-hooks were welded to the top edge of the frame and spaced 48.5 cm apart to hang the pulleys (1-1/4 in Nickel-Plated Fixed Pulley, Everbilt, Home Depot, Atlanta, GA, USA) from. One strip of vinyl-coated wire rope (1/16 in Galvanized Vinyl Coated Steel Wire Rope, Everbilt, Home Depot, Atlanta, GA, USA) was laced through each of the pulleys. One end of this wire rope was attached to the plywood barrier base through the hole drilled in the top of the wood and fastened using a rope clip (1/16 in Wire Rope Clip in Zinc-Plated, Hardware Essentials, Home Depot, Atlanta, GA, USA). The other end of the wire rope was first stripped of its vinyl coating 2.54cm from the end, and then attached to a wire ring terminal (Insulated Wire Ring Terminal, Ace Hardware, Oak Brooke, IL, USA) using wire crimpers. This wire ring terminal was connected to the feed bin by looping it around a pre-existing screw and securing it using the pre-existing nut.

Figure 3. Electrical wiring schematic for powering the animal shocker (Precision Animal Shocker, model no. H13-17A, Coulburn Instruments, Holliston, MA, USA), which was used to apply a current to the barrier (Figure 2). The motion sensor (1) that detected when an animal approached the shocker was connected to the wall outlet using 14/2 outdoor electrical wire (50-ft 14/2 Solid UF-B Wire, Southwire, Carrollton, GA, USA) (2). The wire made a 3-way connection with a spliced power cable (3), the male end of which plugged into the wall outlet and the female end into the animal shocker (4). This device has a current output range of 1-5000 μ A and connected to the barrier via a cable with two alligator clips that attached to the barrier (50 ft Shock Cable, 2-pole, universal clips, Coulburn Instruments, Holliston, MA, USA). The alligator clips (5) were each attached to a separate piece of chicken wire (Figure 2, #4) to avoid shorting the current produced by the animal shocker. The motion sensor was fixed to the top of the pulley system frame (Figure 1, #2) and angled towards the pen so that the device only turned on when the animal was in close proximity to the barrier. To trigger the current to be produced by the animal shocker, the “MANUAL TRIGGER” button on the shocker must be pressed. To eliminate the need for someone to manually administer the shock every time an animal approached, a platform was created that had an arm designed to hold the “MANUAL TRIGGER” button down. When an animal triggered the motion sensor to turn the animal shocker on, the button was already pressed down by the arm, automatically administering the shocking current to the barrier. After 30 minutes of no motion, the motion sensor shut off, which also powered down the animal shocker and the barrier was no longer electrified. Arrows in figure indicate wired connections, fastened with standard wire connectors; color-matching is important to ensure proper electrical grounding and device functionality.